

Evaluation of storage stability for biocrude derived from hydrothermal liquefaction of microalgae

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Abstract

The instability of hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) biocrude has impeded the broader utilization of fuel and chemical feedstock. In this paper, we investigated the storage stability of biocrude produced from HTL of microalgae. The biocrude showed

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5 good stability in phase homogeneity and water content, whereas the viscosity and av-
6 erage molecular weight increased by 48.4 and 41.9%, respectively, after storing for 12
7 months. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and asphaltene content analysis indicated
8 more high-boiling-point fraction, and asphaltene fraction appeared in biocrude during
9 storage. Further element analysis and increased total acid numbers (TAN) demon-
10 strated oxidization, and acidic-compounds-forming reactions occurred, and the Gas
11 chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) results evidenced this guess. However,
12 the mechanism of biocrude storage instability still needs further analysis. The current
13 biocrude assuredly requires stabilization refining for future applications.

14 Introduction

15 The third generation of biomass microalgae is considered a promising resource of sustain-
16 able fuel.¹ Hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of microalgae is a thermochemical conversion
17 process occurred in subcritical or supercritical water.²⁻⁴ During the HTL process, polymeric
18 biochemical macrocompounds (such as hydrocarbons, proteins, and lipids) in microalgae
19 biomass were thermally cracked into numerous small molecules and converted into a liquid
20 called biocrude eventually.⁵ The HTL process converts the whole biochemical compositions
21 in the microalgae biomass into biocrude, making the thermal conversion process more effec-
22 tive than the only-lipid-used-interesterification biodiesel production.⁶ The HTL conversion
23 of microalgae liquefied the wet aqueous biomass microalgae without the feedstock drying
24 cost.⁷⁻¹⁰ Moreover, the HTL process was carried out in a milder condition than pyroly-
25 sis and gasification methods requiring a higher equipment requirement.¹¹ These advantages
26 above made HTL a promising technology for microalgae-derived biofuel production. Also,
27 the microalgae biocrude produced from HTL has a higher energy density (26 - 38 MJ kg⁻¹)
28 and a less moisture content (1 - 8%) than that of bio-oil from pyrolysis (15 - 30%).¹²⁻¹⁴ The
29 produced biocrude could be directly used or upgraded into liquid fuel and chemical materials.
30 From a long-term perspective, biocrude is with a broader market prospect.

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4 31 However, compared with petroleum crude oil, the biocrude is physically unstable and
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6 32 chemically reactive due to the complex composition and high content of oxygen-containing
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8 33 functional groups.^{15,16} Previous research indicated that the HTL biocrude is a complex mix-
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10 34 ture of thousands of organic compounds and has a wide range of boiling points.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ These
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12 35 compounds, however, were produced before reaching a thermodynamical equilibrium and are
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14 36 considered highly chemically active. This negative property led to the gradual changes in the
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16 37 physical and chemical properties of HTL biocrude, especially under storage and transport.²⁰
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18 38 Therefore, the HTL biocrude is hard to maintain its stability, and this situation has been a
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20 39 bottleneck for the further application of biocrude. Hence, researchers introduced the term
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22 40 of biocrude stability for evaluating the ability of biocrude to maintain the original physical
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24 41 and chemical properties during storage over an extent of a period of time, especially without
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26 42 significant degradation.²¹ The storage stability is considered a crucial factor of biocrude and
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28 43 showed a significant effect on the industrial applications of biocrude in the future.²²

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30 44 In the past decades, many researchers focused on measuring and discussing the storage
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32 45 stability of bio-oil produced from pyrolysis of woody biomass. Various parameters such
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34 46 as water content, viscosity, average molecular weight, were chosen to evaluate the storage
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36 47 stability of the pyrolysis bio-oil.¹⁵ However, little works focus on the storage stability of
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38 48 biocrude from the HTL process until recently,²³⁻²⁶ while the continuous and pilot-scale HTL
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40 49 operating is rapidly developing.²⁷⁻³⁰ Therefore, there is an urgent assessment demand for
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42 50 the practical application of biocrude, and a discussion about the storage stability of HTL
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44 51 biocrude should be given.

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46 52 In this paper, systematic experiments were carried out to determine the storage stability
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48 53 of biocrude obtained from HTL of microalgae. Fresh biocrude samples from HTL of microal-
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50 54 gae were subjected to the storage test for 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. Characterization of the
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52 55 physical and chemical properties of the biocrude samples was conducted. The changes in
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54 56 the stored biocrude and the storage stability of the biocrude were analyzed.

Materials and method

Biocrude preparation

The biocrude samples used in this research were produced from the hydrothermal liquefaction of microalgae *Nannochloropsis* purchased from Shandong Yantai HaiRong Biology Technology Co., Ltd. (Shandong, China.) The element content of carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur in the dry ash-free organic matter of microalgae is 47.55, 8.77, 31.68, 9.97, and 2.08%, respectively. A high-pressure batch reactor (GS-2.0, Weihai Chemical Machinery Co., Ltd., China) was used in the HTL process. This reactor was made of 316 stainless steel with a volume capacity of 2.0 liters. The reactor vessel was heated with an external electrical furnace. A detailed description of HTL and product separation operation was presented in our previous study.³¹ The HTL process was carried out at 300 °C with a holding time of 30 min. the obtained biocrude yield was 41.02%. The obtained biocrude was a viscous black liquid with a smoky smell and was used to further storage stability tests.

Storage stability experimental process

The fresh biocrude samples were well homogenized for 60 min before experiments. The storage experiment was carried out at room temperature (25 °C) for 0, 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. The biocrude without a period of storage time was labeled as fresh biocrude. Fresh biocrude was stored in a sealed bottle, and we weighted the bottle and biocrude at zero time. After each period of storage time, the sealed bottle was weighted again before opening. Each experiment was duplicated or triplicated for each period, and the data shown represent the average value of the independent measurement.

Characterization methods

The kinematic viscosity of the biocrude sample was measured with a viscometer (DV-III, Brookfield, USA) and based on a modified ASTM-D 2983-2017 method,³² as we described

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4 81 somewhere else.³² In each measurement test, a circulating bath of ethylene glycol coolant
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6 82 was used to keep the constant temperature from 10 to 60 °C, with an accuracy of 1 °C. The
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8 83 measurement was repeated twice, and the average viscosity was reported.

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10 84 Volumetric Karl Fischer titration was used to measure the moisture content of the
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12 85 biocrude. A Metrohm 701 KF Titrino (Brinkmann Instruments, Inc., NY, USA) and Hy-
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14 86 dranal Composite 5 reagents were used. About 1 g of oil samples were titrated in a solvent
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16 87 mixture of 40 mL of methanol and 20 mL of toluene.

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18 88 The average molecular weight (AMW) was measured with high-performance liquid chro-
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20 89 matography (HPLC, Agilent 1200, Agilent, USA), with a Waters styrylgel HR1 column and
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22 90 UV detector. The analysis was carried out at 40 °C, and tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as
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24 91 the eluent with a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹. The AMW was calculated based on determination
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26 92 methods reported by Baumberger et al.³³ The analyses were repeated at least twice, and the
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28 93 average AMW was reported.

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30 94 The total acid number (TAN) of biocrude was measured with the color indicator phe-
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32 95 nolpthalein and based on a modified EN 14104 standard method.¹³ 25 mg of biocrude was
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34 96 dissolved in 5 mL of isopropyl alcohol and then titrated by potassium hydroxide (KOH) so-
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36 97 lution of 20 mM with the color indicator phenolphthalein at room temperature (25 °C). The
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38 98 experimental errors are less than 0.1% after repeating the titration process which was at
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40 99 least three times and presented as the average value.

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42 100 Elemental contents of C, H, N, and S in the biocrude samples were carried out on an
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44 101 elemental analyzer (VARIO EL III, Elementar, Germany). The content of O was determined
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46 102 by difference. The higher heating value (HHV) of the sample was calculated as previous
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48 103 literature.³¹

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50 104 A TG analyzer (DTG-60, Shimadzu, Japan) was used for the thermal gravimetric anal-
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52 105 ysis (TGA). A sample (10 ± 0.5 mg) was heated from 50 to 500 °C with a heating rate of
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54 106 10 °C min⁻¹ and in a 50 mL min⁻¹ pure nitrogen flow. Each experiment was repeated at least
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56 107 three times to ensure reproducibility and presented the average value. The experiment errors

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3 are less than 0.1%.
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6 109 Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS, QP2010, Shimadzu Co., Japan) was
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8 110 used for characterizing the organic composition of biocrude samples. A Varian DB-5 column
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10 111 (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m) was used, while helium was the carrier gas. The injection
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12 112 temperature and interface temperature were set at 250 $^{\circ}$ C and 320 $^{\circ}$ C, respectively. The
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14 113 column temperature was at 50 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 min, then ramped up at a rate of 10 $^{\circ}$ C min $^{-1}$ to
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16 114 120 $^{\circ}$ C and maintained for 1 min, afterward increased to 250 $^{\circ}$ C with the same heating rate
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18 115 and maintained for 20 min. The ion source was heated to 200 $^{\circ}$ C. The mass spectrometer
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20 116 was operated in positive electron impact mode (EI) at 70 eV. Scan range of mass spectrum
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22 117 was in m/z of 20 - 650. All chromatogram peaks in spectra were compared with the electron
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24 118 impact mass spectrum from NIST Database (NIST11). Analysis of the content of asphaltene
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26 119 fractions in the biocrude samples was based on a modified ASTM D-2007-19 method. The
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28 120 asphaltene was defined as the n-hexane insoluble but toluene soluble fraction.
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31 **Results and discussion**

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35 **The general phenomenon observed after the storage of biocrude**

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38 123 The fresh biocrude was analyzed prior to the storage process, and all the data were used as
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40 124 the control group. No weight change of the sum weight of the biocrude and storing bottle was
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42 125 observed before and after a period of storage time. The results indicated that only internal
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44 126 reactions could occur during the storage process. Since we stored the biocrude samples in
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46 127 dark and under constant temperature conditions; hence the extent of the storage period can
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48 128 be considered the only influential factor for the changed properties and composition of the
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50 129 HTL biocrude in the storage process.

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52 130 For all biocrude samples, no phase separation was observed through the storage periods,
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54 131 while the phase separation appeared in storage stability tests of pyrolysis bio-oil.³⁴ Much
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56 132 lower water content in biocrude than that in the pyrolysis bio-oil could be the reason. The
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3 133 lower water content in the HTL biocrude could conduce to the homogeneity of biocrude and
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5 134 retard the phase separation during storage. In conclusion, the obtained biocrude from HTL
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7 135 of microalgae showed better stability in avoiding phase separation. Meanwhile, we found
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9 136 out that the longer the biocrude was stored, the less flowability the biocrude had. The
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11 137 biocrude seems not good at keeping a stable flowability. Further analysis of viscosity and
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13 138 other properties connected with the flowability would be discussed in detail in the following
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15 139 section.

19 140 **Storage stability evaluation of biocrude**

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22 141 Unlike the physically and chemically stable fossil fuels, biomass-derived liquid fuel usually
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24 142 changes its physical and chemical properties during storage.³⁵⁻³⁷ Various parameters were
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26 143 widely used to assess the storage stability of biofuels. Herein, we investigated the changes
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28 144 in the viscosities, the water contents, and the average molecular weights (AMW) of stored
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30 145 biocrude to evaluate the storage stability of biocrude from the HTL of microalgae. Moreover,
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32 146 the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and asphaltene content analysis were also applied.

35 147 **Viscosity**

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38 148 The viscosity of liquid fuel is a key parameter for evaluating the practical application of
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40 149 liquid fuel and the quality of the fuel.³⁸ Herein, we measured the viscosity of the biocrude
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42 150 samples and analyzed the viscosity changes during the storage.

44 151 As shown in Table 1, the viscosity of fresh biocrude was pretty higher than that of py-
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46 152 rolysis bio-oil.³⁹ Further analysis of stored biocrude suggested that the viscosity of biocrude
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48 153 gradually increased after storage. It appeared that the rate of viscosity change, however,
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50 154 changed differently. In the first month, the viscosity increased around 30%, and the rapidly
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52 155 increased viscosity (more than 60 cP per month) suggested that most of the reactions re-
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54 156 sponsible for the viscosity increase occurred during this period. Conversely, the increasing
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56 157 rate of viscosity gradually dropped off in the following eleven months. Despite the fact that

Table 1: Change in oil parameters of fresh and stored biocrude

	Stored time (months)					Fossil Fuel
	0 (Fresh)	1	3	6	12	
Viscosity (cP)	207.5 ± 0.2	269.3 ± 1.3	287.4 ± 2.5	291.8 ± 0.7	307.9 ± 0.8	-
Water content (%)	1.3 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.3	0.1
AMW (Da)	1091.8 ± 2.6	1388.1 ± 3.5	1424.5 ± 1.5	1489.2 ± 0.9	1549.7 ± 1.1	-
Asphaltene content (%)	33.6 ± 0.4	42.5 ± 0.7	45.2 ± 1.3	43.6 ± 2.9	46.1 ± 1.7	-

we observed a downhill in the increasing rate of viscosity, the keep-on increased viscosity (by 48.4%) suggested that these viscosity-increasing reactions might be retarded but still be apparent during the rest of time. In conclusion, the biocrude showed an unpleasant instability in viscosity during storage.

As widely known, the increased viscosity of biocrude with the extent of storage duration would lead to poor combustion, increase the engine deposits, and require more energy to liquid fuel pumping.⁴⁰ Worse still, the high-viscosity biocrude might result in an increased carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned hydrocarbon (UHC).⁴¹ In order to make the utilization of biocrude more economical and environmentally friendly, further stabilization refining of biocrude is needed and necessary.

Water content

The water content of biocrude could affect the physicochemical properties of biocrude and showed a positive or negative influence based on diverse applications.⁴²⁻⁴⁴ A high water content would reduce the heating value and the homogeneity of biocrude and its solubility in fossil-based fuels, whereas a moderate water content might benefit the viscosity of biocrude.^{45,46} Currently, the water content has been another signal index to the stability of biofuels. Hence, we evaluated the water content of the biocrude during the storage.

The water content of biocrude before and after a period of storage time was presented in Table 1. Generally, the water content slightly increased from 1.3% to 3.4% after 12

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3 177 months of storage at room temperature. This observation is consistent with previous liter-
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5 178 ature.²³ The high-water content could be used as evidence of condensation reactions upon
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7 179 storage.^{47,48} However, due to the lower water content of HTL biocrude, a slight increase in
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9 180 water content after storage hardly reduced the viscosity of biocrude and showed no effect on
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11 181 the homogeneity of biocrude, as we described in section .

12 13 14 15 182 **Average molecular weight (AMW)**

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17 183 In addition to the main reason for stored biocrude viscosity-increasing, the average molecular
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19 184 weight (AMW) of the stored biocrude could also determine the storage stability of biocrude.⁴⁷
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21 185 The measurement of AMW could provide a rough idea of the biocrude quality. We desired a
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23 186 smaller AMW biocrude, which would be easier for refining and transport.⁴⁹ In this section,
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25 187 we used high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) to measure the AMW of the
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27 188 biocrude.

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29 189 As shown in Table 1, the AMW of HTL microalgae biocrude showed a trend of increase
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31 190 during storage. An AMW of fresh biocrude sustainably increased 41.9% after 12-month
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33 191 storage, indicating the formation of larger molecules. The increase of AMW was accelerated
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35 192 in the first month, and this general trend is consistent with the observation in the measure-
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37 193 ment of biocrude viscosity. A significant origin of the bigger molecular weight compounds
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39 194 could be the condensation reactions, and the increased AMW could agree with the water
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41 195 content analysis. However, analyzing the detailed kinetics of reactions associated with the
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43 196 increase of biocrude AMW is impossible due to the highly complex composition of biocrude
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45 197 consisting of more than thousands of kinds of organic compounds.¹⁷ Moreover, besides the
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47 198 polymerization and dehydration condensation reactions, innumerable parallel and consecu-
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49 199 tive chemical reactions occurred in the initial biocrude and between the intermediates and in
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51 200 the final products.⁵ It is impossible to identify and model individual reactions. In that case,
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53 201 other advanced methods should be introduced in the separation and identification of HTL
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55 202 biocrude for better composition and kinetics understanding. Besides, the heavier AMW led

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3 203 to a higher viscosity and suggested there might be more heavy fractions such as asphaltene
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5 204 and difficult-volatilization fractions in the stored biocrude.
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8 205 **Asphaltene content and boiling point distribution**

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11 206 The TGA method is widely applied in estimating the boiling point distribution of biofuels
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13 207 from thermochemical conversion. The TGA process could be regarded as a mini-distillation
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15 208 operation and provide a comparative assessment of different biocrude samples. In Table 2,
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17 209 we presented the boiling point distribution of all the biocrude samples, while the asphaltene
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19 210 contents were also provided in Table 1.

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22 211 As shown in Table 2, the storage treatment did show an influence on the distribution
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24 212 of the boiling point. The fraction with a boiling point less than 350 °C (usually defined
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26 213 as the light fraction) decreased from 70.1 to 61.83% in a month and then fluctuated in
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28 214 a small range, whereas the heavy fraction (boiling point ≥ 350 °C) increased accordingly.
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30 215 The changed distribution suggested that more high-boiling-point fractions appeared in the
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32 216 biocrude samples after storage, and the increased asphaltene content (from 33.6 to 44.1%)
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34 217 firmly supported this trend. According to Jampolski et al.,⁵⁰ the decreased content of light
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36 218 volatile could be attributed to the increased viscosity, while the higher content of heavy
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38 219 fractions, which came from the polymerization reactions, might also lead to a more viscous
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40 220 biocrude.

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42 221 In conclusion, comparing the biocrude samples with different storage periods, unstable
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44 222 storage stability was observed in the current HTL biocrude. Further upgrading should be
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46 223 taken to improve the stability of biocrude in the future. The possible chemical changes that
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48 224 occurred in the storage process would be discussed in the following section .
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51 225 **Chemical compositions of biocrude samples**

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54 226 A stable biocrude should have less compositional variance after storage. However, as the
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56 227 result of internal reactions during storage, the chemical properties and composition of stored
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Table 2: Boiling point distribution of the biocrude samples

Temperature range (°C)	Estimated boiling point range of biocrude (wt %)				
	Fresh	1 month	3 months	6 months	12 months
≤ 250	54.69	48.22	44.65	42.48	44.34
250 - 350	15.41	13.61	15.26	19.39	15.83
350 - 500	15.72	17.85	16.74	18.45	19.67
≥ 500	14.18	20.32	23.35	19.68	20.16
Total fraction (%) of light fraction (boiling point ≤ 350 °C)					
	70.10	61.83	59.91	61.87	60.17

biocrude changed accordingly. Herein, we analyzed the elemental composition, total acid number (TAN), and the GC-MS characterization results of the biocrude samples to determine the chemical changes in biocrude.

Element analysis

The changes in the elemental composition of biocrude can provide a rough sight of the trend about the types of reactions during the storage of HTL biocrude. According to the elemental analysis results in Table 3, slight changes of elemental composition were observed during the storage. As can be seen, the carbon (C) and hydrogen (H) content fluctuated in a small range. However, the oxygen content gradually increased a bit from 14.5 to 15.4%. Moreover, the O/C ratio increased from 0.15 to 0.17 after storage, while the H/C ratio changed relatively slightly. The changed element ratios demonstrated that there might be oxidation reactions that occurred during storage.²³ The oxidation reactions could come from the air atmosphere in the storage bottles. Meanwhile, the elemental contents of both nitrogen and sulfur maintained steady, which might indicate that no obvious dinitrogen or desulfuration reactions happened during storage. The relatively stable elemental content of C, H, N, S, and the little-increased O content could demonstrate the HTL biocrude from microalgae is relatively stable. Notably, the HHVs of biocrude hardly changed because of the slight change of element composition of biocrude. It seems that storage in the long-term would not affect

Table 3: Element composition and TAN analysis of the biocrude samples

Element Content (%)	Stored time (months)					Fossil Fuel
	0 (Fresh)	1	3	6	12	
Carbon	70.22	70.26	69.87	70.01	69.79	8586
Hydrogen	7.57	7.61	7.56	7.42	7.39	12.5-14
Nitrogen	7.49	7.31	7.57	7.53	7.22	0.2
Sulfur	0.22	0.26	0.28	0.22	0.20	>1
Oxygen ^d	14.50	14.56	14.72	14.82	15.40	1
HHV (MJ/kg)	32.58	32.64	32.44	32.29	32.10	3942
O/C ratio	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.01
H/C ratio	1.29	1.30	1.30	1.27	1.27	1.82
TAN (mg KOH g ⁻¹)	210.23	256.87	254.15	259.78	258.26	<0.5

^d calculated by differences

the heating value of HTL biocrude, which favored the application of HTL biocrude as an alternative feedstock of liquid fuel. However, the slight increase in the oxygen content of biocrude after storage, which has been higher than that in fossil fuel,³⁸ might cause some concern. Therefore, further characterization in the total acid number and chemical composition was carried out to identify whether there would be any undesired changes in the chemical composition of HTL biocrude after storage.

Total acid number (TAN) analysis

The high acidity of unconventional and renewable liquid fuel is a serious problem in storage and transportation. Therefore, the total acid number (TAN) is introduced and widely used to indicate the acidity of liquid fuel. TAN is defined as the milligrams of potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the acid in a gram of sample. The measurement of TAN has been widely used to evaluate the acidity of biocrude, biodiesel, lubricating oils, heavy oil, bitumen, and fats. In this section, the TAN of fresh biocrude was measured and compared with those of biocrude stored for several months.

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4 260 As shown in Table 3, the TAN of the biocrude samples generally increased after storing
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6 261 for a month. The increased TAN could come from the internal reactions, which produced
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8 262 organic acids during storage. A similar phenomenon was observed in accelerated aged bio-
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10 263 oil, as the pH of the bio-oil decreased.⁴⁸ The organic acids might come from the oxidation
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12 264 reactions of alcohol and aldehyde,⁵¹ and this explanation might be well consistent with the
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14 265 slightly increased oxygen content mentioned in the elemental analysis above. However, when
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16 266 the storage time was longer than a month, hardly any differences in TAN of biocrude samples
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18 267 were observed with the extended periods of storage time. The increased but steady TAN of
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20 268 biocrude could indicate that the production of organic acids might finish in a shorter period
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22 269 of time, and an even longer extent of storage time could not affect the TAN of biocrude.⁵²

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24 270 Notably, the TANs of both fresh and stored biocrude were far higher than that of standard
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26 271 commercial fossil fuel (no more than $0.5 \text{ mg KOH g}^{-1}$).⁵³ Such high values of TAN in biocrude
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28 272 might cause corrosion to power machinery and storage facilities. Further deacidification
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30 273 upgrading of biocrude should be taken into consideration.

31 32 274 **GC-MS analysis**

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35 275 Based on the element analysis and TAN measurement results above, the stored biocrude
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37 276 should have changed its chemical composition during the storage process. Herein, we ana-
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39 277 lyzed the chemical composition of the biocrude samples and tried to identify the molecular
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41 278 changes after storage by GC-MS. It should be noted that the biocrude contains a high con-
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43 279 tent of high-boiling-point fractions, and these fractions could not volatilize in the vaporizing
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45 280 chamber of GC and be identified by GC-MS. Therefore, the GC-MS could only be used as
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47 281 a qualitative analysis but still provide helpful information about the chemical composition
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49 282 changes during the biocrude storage.

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51 283 According to the results above, we chose the fresh biocrude and the biocrude stored for
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53 284 one and six months to identify their chemical compositions because of the most changed
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55 285 biocrude properties and a leveling storage stability, respectively. To simplify the comparison

Figure 1: Group fraction distribution of fresh and stored biocrude samples (CH: chain hydrocarbons)

and discussion, we classified the identified compounds into several groups: chain alkanes, aromatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, aldehydes and ketones, fatty acids, esters, phenols, and other heteroatomic compounds. The comparison was presented in Fig. 1.

As shown in Fig. 1, the chemical composition of biocrude after storage accordingly changed. Generally, there was an increase in the contents of fatty acids and heterocyclic compounds. The increased content of fatty acids could come from the oxidation or other acid-forming reaction, and the increased content well consisted of the increased TAN observed in the stored biocrude. Accordingly, we found out fewer esters appeared in the identified compounds after storage. The decomposition of esters could explain the decrease, and the decomposition reactions could produce fatty acids and alcohols. However, no alcohol was identified because the oxidation of acids and aldol condensation might occur.^{51,54} That could also explain the disappearance of aldehydes. Moreover, the small quantities of aromatic derived compounds were identified in the fresh biocrude samples. However, they disappeared in the storage process and might undergo the aryl condensation reactions to form bigger molecular weight compounds, as Ben and Diebold found out in their bio-oil after one year of

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3 301 storage.⁵⁵ According to the increased content of heterocyclic compounds, a slight decrease
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5 302 in amide content was observed, which might be due to the intermolecular cyclization.^{56,57}
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7 303 For the identified chain hydrocarbon, the content fluctuated in a small range. It seems that
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9 304 the storage did not affect the chain hydrocarbons.

11 305 Apparently, the fresh biocrude contains plenty of chemically reactive organic compounds,
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13 306 and these fractions did show a chemical instability during storage. However, the GC-MS
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15 307 method could only identify some of the light fractions in all biocrude samples due to the
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17 308 technical limit. More advanced characterization methods, especially for identifying the heavy
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19 309 fraction at the molecular level, should be developed and disseminated.

23 310 **Conclusion**

26 311 The storage stability of biocrude produced from HTL of microalgae was investigated in
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28 312 this paper. The biocrude showed good stability in phase homogeneity and water content,
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30 313 whereas the viscosity increased by 48.4% after storing for 12 months. TGA and fractionation
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32 314 analysis indicated more high-boiling-point fraction and asphaltene fractions appeared in the
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34 315 stored biocrude, which positively affected the future transport of HTL biocrude. Further
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36 316 element analysis and TAN measurement demonstrated oxidization, and acidic-compounds-
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38 317 forming reactions occurred during storage, which can be used to guide the upgrading of HTL
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40 318 biocrude in the future. This conjecture was supported by the composition changes in stored
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42 319 biocrude from GC-MS analysis.

46 320 **Conflicts of interest**

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50 321 There are no conflicts to declare.

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481 **TOC Graphic**

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